

Synthesis of some isoindole-1,3-dione and amino-oxyalkyl derivatives of benzimidazole

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2-(Bromoalkoxy)-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-diones are condensed with benzimidazole and its derivatives to give 2-[(benzimidazole-1-yl)-alkoxy]-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-diones. Hydrolysis under acidic conditions gives the corresponding amino-oxy compounds.

A wide range of chemotherapeutic potentialities are found to be associated with benzimidazole derivatives¹ and also with isoindole-1,3-dione and amino-oxy compounds². Hence it was thought useful to undertake the synthesis of some alkoxy-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-dione and amino-oxyalkyl derivatives of benzimidazole (4 and 5).

Results and Discussion

Phthalic anhydride (1) was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of sodium carbonate in an aqueous media to give 2-hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-dione³. The latter was treated with terminal dibromoalkanes to give 2-(bromoalkoxy)-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-dione (2; $n = 2, 3, 4$)⁴. Condensation of the benzimidazole derivatives (3) with 2 gave 2-[(benzimidazol-1-yl)alkoxy]-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-diones (4a-f). Compounds 4a-f were hydrolysed to the corresponding amino-oxy compounds (5a-f).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was tested by TLC. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra ($CDCl_3/CF_3COOH$) on a Varian spectrometer (270 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard.

2-Hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-dione³ and 2-(bromoalkoxy)-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-dione (2)⁴ were prepared by reported methods.

2-[(Benzimidazol-1-yl)alkoxy]-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-diones (4a-f): A solution of benzimidazole and its derivatives (0.01 mol) and 2 (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. Anhyd. K_2CO_3 (0.01 mol) was added slowly and the reflux continued for 15 h. It was then filtered, solvent evaporated and the solid obtained was dried and crystallised: **4a** (85%), m.p. 155°, ν_{max} 2939 (CH_2), 1770 (CO-N-CO), 1456 (C=C Ar), 1301–1244 cm^{-1} (O-N), m/z M^+ 307 (18), 190 (24), 162 (11), 130 (100), δ 8.22 (1H, s, CH), 7.2–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 2.8 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.2 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, O-CH₂); **b** (80%), 146°, ν_{max} 1780–1760 (CO-N-CO), 1462 (C=C Ar), 1282 cm^{-1} (O-N), m/z M^+ 321 (11), 204 (18), 162 (21), 130 (100), δ 8.2 (1H, s, CH), 7.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 2.6 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.3 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.6–2.8, (2H, p, J 6.22 Hz, C-CH₂-C); **c** (55%), 140°, ν_{max} 1740 (CO-N-CO), 1554 (C=N), 1458 (C=C Ar), 1245 cm^{-1} (O-N), δ 8.22 (1H, s, CH), 7.3–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 2.7 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.2 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.5–2.7 (4H, m, C-CH₂-CH₂-C); **d** (75%), 145° ν_{max} 1793–1751 (CO-N-CO), 1523 (C=N), 1280 cm^{-1} (O-N), m/z M^+ 321 (9.3), 190 (15), 162 (100), 130 (32), δ 1.95 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2–7.7 (8H, m, ArH), 2.9 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.2–3.4 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, O-CH₂); **e** (70%), 132°, δ 1.90 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 2.8 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.2 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.5 (2H, p, J 6.2 Hz, C-CH₂-C); **f** (52%), 120°, δ 1.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 2.8 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.2 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.8 (4H, m, C-CH₂-CH₂-C).

Note

Amino oxyalkyl benzimidazoles (5a-f) Compounds **4a-f** were boiled in a mixture of glacial acetic acid and 12 N HCl (2:3) for 30 min. On cooling, phthalic acid separated was filtered. The filtrate on evaporation under reduced pressure gave solid products which were dried and crystallised. **5a** (65%), m.p. 192°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3030–2992 (NH₃⁺), 2921 (CH₂), 1540 cm⁻¹ (C=N), δ 8.19 (1H, s, CH), 7.1–7.7 (4H, s, ArH), 2.7 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.4 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 8.9–9.1 (3H, s, NH₃⁺), **b** (52%), 196°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3040–3000 (NH₃⁺), 2920 (CH₂), 1550 cm⁻¹ (C=N), δ 8.15 (1H, s, CH), 7.2–7.9 (4H, s, ArH), 2.7 (2H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.3 (2H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.5–2.7 (2H, p, *J* 6.2 Hz, C-CH₂-C), 8.8 (3H, s, NH₃⁺), **c** (60%), 199°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3020 (NH₃⁺), 2929 (CH₂), 1528 cm⁻¹ (C=N), δ 8.1 (1H, s, CH), 7.2–7.6 (4H, s, ArH), 2.5 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.2 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.4 (4H, m, C-CH₂-CH₂-C), 8.5–9.2 (3H, s, NH₃⁺), **d** (57%), 162°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3000 (NH₃⁺), 2935 (CH₂), 1545 cm⁻¹ (C=N), δ 1.92 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1–7.7 (4H, s, ArH), 2.7 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.4 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, O-CH₂), 8.7 (3H, s, NH₃⁺), **e** (68%), 164°, δ 1.9 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2–7.4 (4H, s, ArH), 2.7 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.4 (2H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.5–2.8 (2H, p, *J* 6.2 Hz, C-CH₂-C), 8.8 (3H,

s, NH₃⁺), **f** (43%), 169°, δ 1.95 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1–7.5 (4H, s, ArH), 2.5 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.2 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, O-CH₂), 2.4–2.7 (4H, m, C-CH₂-CH₂-C), 8.7 (3H, s, NH₃⁺)

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